

Scaling Nanophotonic Interferometric Biosensors toward Parallel Detection of Multiple Biomarkers

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Cite This: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.6c01059>

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ABSTRACT: Silicon photonics has emerged as a promising technology for next-generation biosensors. Its CMOS compatibility, miniaturization, and large-scale fabrication capabilities, combined with high sensitivity, fast response, and inherent label-free detection capabilities, have positioned this technology at the forefront for the deployment of point-of-care (PoC) analytical platforms. However, operating a multiplexed photonic biosensor configuration remains challenging due to limitations such as efficient light coupling to multiple sensing elements, simultaneous signal acquisition, precise microfluidics and biofunctionalization, and optical crosstalk management between sensors. In this study, we introduce an interferometric biosensor that incorporates a new multiplexed nanophotonic bimodal waveguide (BiMW) chip with a compatible microfluidic system and an optimized light-coupling and readout configuration that enables simultaneous, individual detection of up to seven targets in the same sample. All system components have been incorporated into a compact prototype providing an outstanding bulk limit of detection (LOD) of $(7 \pm 5) \times 10^{-7}$ RIU. The biosensor capabilities have been validated against a representative clinical scenario, demonstrating effective and sensitive detection of Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) nucleoproteins relevant to infectious disease diagnostics, achieving a simultaneous LOD of 1.2 ± 0.4 ng·mL⁻¹ across all seven sensors.

KEYWORDS: multiplexed biosensor, silicon photonics, interferometer, microfluidics system, photodetector array, respiratory syncytial virus (RSV)

Silicon photonics has rapidly progressed in recent years, becoming a key enabling technology in diverse applications, including communications,¹ quantum computing,² light detection and ranging (LIDAR) technology,³ industrial sensing,⁴ and biosensing.⁵ Its compatibility with complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) fabrication, large-scale manufacturing capabilities, cost-effectiveness, and high level of miniaturization have positioned silicon photonics as a versatile platform for next-generation integration technologies. In the field of biosensors, silicon photonics has steadily advanced, combining high integration, sensitivity, rapid operation, and fast response, along with inherent label-free detection capabilities, establishing it as an advanced technology for the true deployment of point-of-care (PoC) analytical platforms for both clinical diagnostics and environmental applications.

Numerous photonic biosensors have been studied in recent years, mainly based on the evanescent field working principle, employing several building blocks such as microring resonators,^{6–8} photonic crystals,^{9–11} or optical interferometric configurations such as Mach-Zehnder interferometers (MZI),^{12–14} and bimodal waveguide (BiMW)^{15–17} interferometers. Designed to achieve high sensitivity with minimal footprint, these configurations have been incorporated into

sensing systems with variable levels of integration and compactness, and demonstrated their applicability for the detection of target analytes in clinical diagnostics,¹⁵ environmental monitoring,^{18,19} and food industry^{20,21} analysis. Among them, interferometric configurations have reported the highest sensitivity, achieving bulk limit of detection (LOD) in the range of 10^{-7} – 10^{-8} refractive index units (RIU).^{22,23} BiMW interferometers are positioned as a leading approach, as they significantly reduce design and fabrication complexity compared with MZIs by integrating the reference and the sensing arms into a single waveguide.

Driven by the increasing complexity and requirements in bioanalysis, especially in clinical diagnostics, where improved specificity and sensitivity are becoming necessary for personalized diagnostics, a growing focus in this field is multiplexed

Received: March 11, 2026

Revised: June 8, 2026

Accepted: June 9, 2026

detection, where multiple target biomarkers are monitored simultaneously in the same sample. While chip layouts often incorporate arrays of multiple sensors, realizing true parallel biosensing and readouts remains challenging. Key limitations include efficient light coupling to multiple sensing elements, simultaneous signal acquisition, precise microfluidics and bio-functionalization, and optical crosstalk management between sensors.

Achieving a reliable multiplexing biosensor also requires addressing challenges such as nonspecific binding and cross-contamination between sensing areas, which can hinder accurate signal deconvolution and quantification. This, in turn, demands controlled biofunctionalization strategies and dedicated microfluidics systems to ensure robust and sensitive detection. Integrating all these components, with electronics and data acquisition systems, into functional PoC devices remains complex, limiting the progress of advanced PoC prototypes for specific applications and their deployment in clinical or environmental control settings^{22,24,25} (see Table S1).

One of the earliest advancements in multiplexed photonic configurations was based on broadband MZIs.¹² This platform integrated a total of ten sensors, each integrating the light source, an arrayed waveguide grating (AWG) spectral analyzer, and a photodiode array directly on chip. Nevertheless, its validation was performed only through the detection of three targets.²⁶ While this approach enables high level of integration, it entails substantial fabrication costs, representing a major barrier to large-scale commercialization.

Multiplexing capabilities have also been explored using ring resonators, achieving the simultaneous analysis of five different analytes.^{27,28} However, in addition to their inferior sensitivity compared to interferometric architectures, this technology relies on expensive components, such as tunable lasers or spectrometers, which complicates the development of a cost-effective PoC device.

A significant improvement was achieved by Martens et al., who developed a PoC platform based on six MZIs with grating couplers for light in-coupling and a spectral filter based on asymmetric waveguides to facilitate signal readout using a camera.²⁹ The system integrated all electronics, microfluidics, and user interface into a single platform. However, the device was validated with only one target.³⁰ Similarly, Chatzipetrou et al. developed a fully integrated multiplexed device based on six

MZIs with all the required components.³¹ In this case, validation was performed only with two biomarkers.

We have previously introduced a BiMW interferometer sensor and implemented a sensor prototype that provides excellent optical performance at the single-sensor level, and excellent and reproducible biosensing capabilities.^{16,32} However, the architecture was not optimized for multiplexed operation. Extending the optimized configuration to enable reliable, simultaneous measurements across multiple sensors requires both architectural design and proper design of dedicated microfluidics and readout systems.

We address these challenges by introducing a nanophotonic interferometric biosensor that incorporates a new multiplexed nanophotonic BiMW chip with a compatible polymer microfluidic system and optimized light coupling and readout configurations. The nanophotonic chip incorporating the bimodal waveguides is fabricated by CMOS-compatible microfabrication techniques and integrates an on-chip beam-splitting system for straightforward, evenly distributed, and efficient coupling of one light input source to up to eight BiMW waveguides in parallel. A customized silicon (Si) photodetector array with an associated miniaturized electronic amplifier has been designed and incorporated, effectively allowing simultaneous individual detection of each waveguide. Addressing its potential for real biosensing applications, a dedicated microfluidic system has been designed and constructed to deliver samples to the multiple BiMW sensors. All system components, including a cost-effective laser diode-based coupling system, have been integrated into a compact prototype that provides an excellent performance while preserving the bulk LOD and detectability comparable to the single-waveguide BiMW version ($2\text{--}5 \times 10^{-7}$ RIU).³² The biosensing capabilities have been validated against a representative clinical scenario, demonstrating effective and sensitive detection of Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) nucleoproteins relevant to infectious disease diagnostics, highlighting its potential for rapid, point-of-care diagnostics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Operational Principle and Sensor Layout

The sensing principle relies on the interference generated by the interaction of two polarized light propagation modes within the same straight waveguide (see Figure 1). To achieve this, the incoming light

Figure 1. (a) Schematic representation of the BiMW interferometric region, showing the single-mode and bimodal sections. A summary of the sensing principle based on the generation of an interferometric pattern is also shown. (b) Intensity radiation profiles for modes TE₀₀ in the monomodal section, and TE₀₀ and TE₁₀ in the bimodal section. (c) Cross-section design of the BiMW structure and summary of the sensing principle based on the generation of an interferometric pattern are also shown.

is propagated through a single-mode region in the waveguide. At a certain distance, the core thickness increases, acting as a step junction, exciting the first propagation mode. Both modes then start to interfere along the bimodal section, which includes a sensing window etched on the top of the waveguide surface, enabling the interaction between the external medium and the two modes of the light. These two modes exhibit different propagation velocities and evanescent fields penetration depths, resulting in different sensitivities to refractive index changes in the sensing area. The resulting interference pattern of the two modes interaction, modulated by refractive index variations in the sensing area, is collected at the output of the chip.

The new multiplexed BiMW sensor was modelled using Lumerical for modal analysis and Photon Design for the light propagation analysis to facilitate multi-waveguide simultaneous detection. The device was optimized for operation at 660 nm in the visible spectrum due to the low water absorption in this spectral range, ensuring strong light-matter interaction.

Initially, modal analysis of the photonic waveguide was performed to identify monomodal and bimodal structures and to enhance evanescent field interaction in the bimodal design for both TE and TM polarizations. Although TM polarization exhibited slightly stronger interaction, its lower coupling coefficient produces a major experimental signal noise; therefore, TE polarization was ultimately selected (see Figure 1b). The final design consists of silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) rib waveguides ($n_{\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4} = 2.05$) (see Figure 1c). The Si_3N_4 core is deposited over a 2.5 μm silicon oxide (SiO_2) substrate ($n_{\text{SiO}_2} = 1.45$) and buried over a 2 μm SiO_2 cladding. The core thickness is 150 nm in the single-mode section and 340 nm in the bimodal section, the rib width is 2.5 μm , with a rib height ranging from 1 to 3 nm. This Si_3N_4 -based waveguide design exhibits propagation losses below 0.2 dB/cm.³³

The design of the sensor chip includes two main regions (see Figure 2). In the first region, a splitter is designed to divide the incoming light from one to eight distinct single-mode rib waveguides using Y-branch splitters. In the second region, the eight light paths are independently propagated through individual BiMW interferometers. Seven of these waveguides include a sensing window exposed to the

external medium for sensing, while the eighth one serves as a reference waveguide.

The S-shaped Y-branch structures were simulated and optimized to achieve a compact splitter with the lowest splitting losses while ensuring an even power distribution across outputs. The design also accounted for a waveguide spacing of 250 μm to avoid cross-talking between sensors and ensure compatibility with standard photonics industry components. Although this configuration requires long dimensions to minimize bend losses, it ensures a good fabrication tolerance, broadband wavelength independence, and polarization stability compared with alternative configurations such as MMIs, or directional couplers.^{34–36} Simulations were performed by dividing the splitter structure into two regions. The first region consists of a waveguide taper that increases the waveguide width from 2.5 to 5 μm , and the second region comprises the S-shaped branches. Length optimizations of these two structures were performed to achieve equal optical power in both arms and ensure the mode confinement before the BiMW region. The final lengths obtained were 160 and 320 μm for the taper structures, and 3840 and 7680 μm for the S-shaped arms, respectively, obtaining a coupling coefficient of 39% for each branch in both cases (see Figure S2).

To optimize the wafer utilization and maximize the number of fabricated sensors, the final layout consists of nanophotonic chips 50 mm \times 6.75 mm, ($L \times W$), housing three multiplexed sensor groups, each containing eight BiMW waveguides, equally separated by 250 μm from center-to-center. Seven of these waveguides have sensing areas of 15 mm \times 50 μm , while the eighth is embedded in the SiO_2 cladding and serves as a reference. (i.e., 21 sensors per chip). The sensing area lengths were selected to ensure high sensitivity, since the interferometric phase change increases with the sensing length.

Photonic Chip Fabrication

The sensor chips are fabricated at wafer-scale at the ICTS Clean Room facilities Micronanofabs at the Microelectronic National Center (IMB-CNM-CSIC) in Barcelona (Spain). The fabrication process is based on standard microelectronics technology, including

Figure 2. (a) Schematic layout of the multiplexed photonic chip, showing the Y-splitting and BiMW regions, and the sensing area. Each chip integrates three multiplexed sensors; one sensor is highlighted, showing a rendered image of the multiplexed BiMW nanophotonic sensor chip. A picture showing the eight output light spots captured on a CCD camera is also included. (b) Photograph of the multiplexed BiMW nanophotonic sensor chip. (c) Photographs of the sensor chip placed in the experimental setup and the simultaneous light coupling to eight waveguides.

photolithography and etching on 4-in. Si wafers, yielding ten multiplexed BiMW chips per wafer, each containing 3 multiplexed sensors.

The device fabrication begins with a 4-in. p-type Si wafer with a thickness of 500 μm , over which a 2 μm thick layer of thermal oxide is grown. A 340 nm core layer of Si_3N_4 is then deposited via low-pressure chemical vapor deposition (LPCVD). To achieve single-mode waveguides, the Si_3N_4 thickness is reduced from 340 to 150 nm through wet etching. During this step, a hard mask constituted by a layer of SiO_2 , deposited by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) and defined by photolithography, is employed to protect unexposed regions.

The rib waveguide structure is subsequently defined through a combination of standard photolithography and wet etching with buffered hydrofluoric acid (BHF). The low etch rate of BHF for Si_3N_4 ensures precise dimensional control of the rib features. Next, a 200 nm of SiO_2 is deposited by PECVD, followed by the growth of a 100 nm polycrystalline silicon (poly-Si) layer by LPCVD. Dry etching is performed to remove both the poly-Si layer and the upper 150 nm of SiO_2 , ensuring vertical sidewalls. The remaining 50 nm of SiO_2 is subsequently removed by wet etching in BHF. The patterned Poly-Si is employed as an absorbing material to define lateral bands along the waveguide path. Finally, a 1.5 μm PECVD SiO_2 layer is deposited as the top cladding layer. To expose the sensing area, a lithography step is applied, followed by a BHF wet etching step to selectively remove the SiO_2 in the desired regions.

Optical and Electronic System

The multiplexed BiMW setup was implemented employing end-fire coupling to inject light into the photonic chip and a customized photodetector for signal readout at its output. As shown in Figure S1, the nanophotonic sensor chip was placed on a custom aluminum holder with a Peltier temperature controller (TEC3-2.5, Thorlabs) and a 3-axis stage (MBT616D, Thorlabs) to couple the incoming light into the sensor chip. The light source consisted of a laser diode (HL6545MG, Thorlabs) operating at a wavelength of 660 nm, with controlled temperature and current. A spherical lens (C240TMD-B, Thorlabs) was used as a collimator to generate a planar wavefront, and an optical isolator (IO-3D-660-VLP, Thorlabs) was used to protect the laser from undesired back reflections and ensure TE-polarization light, required to achieve higher coupling efficiency. Finally, a 40 \times objective lens (RMS40X, Thorlabs) was used to couple the light into the chip input. The system also includes a neutral density (ND) filter (NES08B-A, Thorlabs) to attenuate the intensity of the coupled light.

For the readout, we have designed a customized Si photodetector array to be placed at the chip output, as no commercial solution exists able to fulfill our requirements. The photodetector array incorporates 8-channel Si photodiodes within an area of 1.8 \times 3.1 mm, consisting of 16 individual photosensitive regions, each measuring 0.05 \times 1.5 mm (Figure 3). This channel configuration allows the individual analysis of up to eight waveguides, each positioned at 250 μm intervals. Each channel includes two distinct regions, upper and lower, separated

by a 0.1 mm gap. This design facilitates accurate analysis of the modal interferometric pattern while minimizing the light intensity from the reference mode (the fundamental mode), which is positioned in the middle of the light spot. To prevent crosstalk between adjacent waveguide outputs, the channels were spaced 200 μm apart, with only 50 μm of active area width. This design was selected after an aperture numeric analysis of different output chips. Moreover, the design included a dummy Si photodiode between the channels to mitigate the electronic crosstalk between channels and reduce noise. The total photodetector size is 15 mm height, 50.8 mm width. The photodetector array fabrication was done by Hamamatsu Photonics (Japan).

The multiple output intensity signals were amplified, conditioned, and converted into a digital signal by an electronic board and a data acquisition card (USB-6361, National Instruments). Following our temporal modulation algorithm based on trigonometric relations,³² the collected interferometric data from the seven simultaneously operated waveguides were automatically processed using a custom Python software, which transforms the interferometric signal into a quantitative phase signal and displays it as a function of time in real-time sensorgrams.

Microfluidic System

The sample flow was driven by a PDMS cell-based microfluidic system integrated onto the multiplexed photonic chip. The microfluidic system also includes a polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) cover, designed to seal the PDMS layer to the sensor chip, preventing leakage and ensuring the uniform distribution of solutions. The system included a syringe injection pump (NE1800, New Era Pump Systems) for buffer delivery and a 6-port injection valve (C22-3186, VICI Valco Instruments) for individual sample injection. The PDMS microfluidic flow cell was designed to allow the sample liquid to flow over each sensor group, thereby delivering a single sample simultaneously over the seven (plus reference) photonic waveguides into the multiplexed photonic chip (Figure 4). Two designs were implemented depending on the sensor group to be evaluated (fabrication is described in the Supporting Information). One design covers the central sensor group, and the other covers both lateral groups. The channel dimensions (400 μm \times 2 mm \times 20 mm, $H \times W \times L$) were selected to match the input microfluidic tube dimensions and allow for a more controlled flow rate (Figure 4a,b). A minimum channel width of 2 mm was selected to ensure homogeneous sample flow in all channels and to prevent noise in the lateral waveguides signal caused by flow disturbances in the vicinity of the PDMS walls. A height of 400 μm was chosen to enhance analyte diffusion while preventing leakage and channel collapse after sealing of the PDMS layer with the PMMA cover. The channel length was selected to completely cover the 15 mm sensing area and to provide sufficient space for the connection of the inlet and outlet microfluidic tubing. Additionally, curved geometries were introduced at the ends of the channel to minimize the risk of bubble accumulation. These dimensions meet the conditions for laminar and diffusion-dominated flow, defined by Reynolds (Re) and Peclet (Pe) numbers of $Re < 100$ and $Pe > 1000$, respectively. For this design, a

Figure 3. (a) Photograph of the photodetector array mounted on the corresponding printed circuit board (PCB). The photosensitive area is highlighted with a microscope image showing 16 Si active regions. (b) Schematic of the photodetector array and photosensitive areas, including device dimensions, and the distribution and size of the active regions.

Figure 4. (a) Design of the one-channel microfluidics. Top image shows the layout for both lateral sensors groups; bottom image shows the layout for the central sensor group. (b) Cross-sectional schematic of the microfluidic channel dimensions, showing the aluminium chip holder, silicon chip, and PDMS polymer. (c) Render of the final microfluidic assembly, highlighting its main components: an aluminium holder for photonic chip placement, a PDMS layer containing the designed channel, a PMMA cover for microfluidics sealing, microfluidic tubes and connectors for sample input and output in the microfluidic channel, and steel pins for microfluidic alignment with the sensor waveguides.

Pe of 5550 for analyte diffusion and a Re of 0.3 were obtained. The PMMA cover features three side holes for screwing and fixing to the chip holder, and two center holes that permit the connection between the microfluidic channel and the input/output tubing. To facilitate the alignment of the microfluidic channels with the photonic waveguides, the design also includes four holes for positioning the taper using metal pins (Figure 4c).

Chips Biofunctionalization and Assay Conditions

The multiplexed nanophotonic chips were cleaned, conditioned, and biofunctionalized with specific antibodies (anti-RSV) as described in the Supporting Information. The real-time detection of the target RSV antigen was performed by flowing different RSV B concentrations (between 10 and 2000 ng·mL⁻¹). After each injection, the sensor surface was regenerated by flowing a NaOH 20 mM solution for 20 s at 20 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Under these conditions, the antibody-coated nanophotonic chip could be reused for up to 20 cycles before degradation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optical Characterization

To evaluate the optical sensing performance of the multiplexed photonic chips and determine the bulk sensitivity, aqueous solutions with different refractive indices were injected through the sensing area of the chip waveguides. Figure 5a shows the real-time modulated sensorgrams acquired from the seven BiMW sensors on one chip after sequential addition of different HCl solutions (0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.25, and 0.5 M). The increase in the interferometric phase change as the HCl concentration increases is clearly visible, with neat linear signals and comparable responses across all sensors.

The corresponding calibration curves (see Figure 5b) were obtained by plotting the phase change ($\Delta\phi$) as a function of the refractive index variation (Δn) relative to the baseline buffer (Milli-Q water). The average bulk sensitivity was determined to

Figure 5. (a) Modulated real-time sensorgrams of the seven multiplexed waveguides in one sensor chip showing the refractive index changes due to the flowing of HCl solutions of different concentrations. (b) Calibration curves of several multiplexed BiMW on different chips, obtained by plotting phase variations ($\Delta\phi$) as a function of the refractive index changes (Δn) for different HCl concentrations relative to the baseline buffer (H₂O). Linear regressions are included for each sensor, with the slope corresponding to the device bulk sensitivity.

be S_{bulk} of $13548 \pm 379 \text{ rad}\cdot\text{RIU}^{-1}$, and the bulk LOD of the system under this configuration (considering three times the phase noise) reached an average value of $(7 \pm 5) \times 10^{-7} \text{ RIU}$, with a signal noise (σ) of $0.003 \pm 0.003 \text{ rad}$, based on the analysis of a total of 21 BiMW sensors (including both inter-chip and intra-chip waveguides). These values represent an outstanding performance and overall sensitivity compared to the current state-of-the-art, and are consistent with the values reported with the singleplex BiMW system when applying this temporal modulation approach ($2\text{--}5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ RIU}$).³²

Biosensor Evaluation

The performance of the multiplexed nanophotonic biosensor was evaluated in terms of intra-waveguide performance by direct targeting the detection of RSV B viral nucleoprotein across all sensors. The simultaneous immobilization with the specific antibody of the seven sensing waveguides was monitored in real time, yielding similar results in all of them, regardless of the waveguide position (see Figure 6). The silanization protocol and conditions for antibody coupling resulted in stable and reproducible immobilization signals; the performance of the seven BiMW sensors exhibits high stability and reproducibility with values of $31.5 \pm 4.1 \text{ rad}$ (CV% of 12.9%). Moreover, the recognition and specific capture of the target RSV B nucleoprotein were addressed by analyzing several concentrations ranging from 10 to 2000 $\text{ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. All measurements were performed using PBST 0.05% as the running buffer and a flow rate of $20 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. These conditions enable rapid assays, with a total measurement time of only 9 min. The reusability of the biofunctionalized multiplexed sensor surface was confirmed by changing the media pH, disrupting the protein-antibody binding. Figure 7 shows the real-time sensorgram for the detection of $1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of RSV B (on) and the subsequent switch to the disrupting solution for regeneration (off). Surface regeneration was achieved by injecting 20 mM NaOH, allowing up to 20 consecutive measurement cycles with the same biofunctionalized surface. Figure 8 presents the calibration curves obtained from the seven BiMW sensors, with each concentration measured in duplicate. From these data,

Figure 6. Real-time sensorgrams of the three-step biofunctionalization protocol (chemical sensor surface activation with EDC/NHS, covalent immobilization of the anti-RSV antibody, and deactivation with ethanolamine) for seven waveguides. Arrows indicate sample injection (ON) and washout (OFF). A double-headed arrow indicates the total phase change associated with the final antibody immobilization.

Figure 7. Real-time sensorgrams of the detection of $1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of RSV B NP (solid line) and $1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of the control CRP protein (dotted line) performed after the sensor chip biofunctionalization with the antibody anti-RSV ($20 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}$).

Figure 8. Calibration curves for RSV B NP detection by the seven multiplexed waveguides in PBST 0.05% buffer. Each analyte concentration was measured in duplicate.

an average LOD of only $1.2 \pm 0.4 \text{ ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ was achieved. Analyte binding specificity was confirmed by flowing C-reactive protein (CRP), a control protein, at a concentration of $1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$, observing a negligible response (see Figure 7). The superior performance of this multiplexed nanophotonic biosensor expands the potential of this platform for demanding applications that require stringent detection limits.

Finally, to assess the reliability of both the multiplexed device and the biosensing strategy, an accurate study was conducted with blind samples (eight samples where concentrations were unknown to the researcher performing the analysis). The validation was performed using two different multiplexed chips, and the results are presented in Figure 9, which compares the real concentration with the measured values. The results show a strong correlation between actual and measured values, yielding average recovery values of 80 and 121% for chips 1 and 2, respectively. These values fall within the 80–120% acceptance criteria for analytical methods, while the R^2 values underscore the precision and linear response of the biosensor, validating the reproducibility and consistency of the BiMW photonic biosensor for multiplexed detection.

Figure 9. Accuracy study of the multiplexed biosensor with blind spiked samples. Linear regression comparing the real analyte concentration with the mean values evaluated by the seven BiMW waveguides of the multiplexed biosensor. The dashed line represents a perfect correlation between both (slope = 1).

CONCLUSIONS

A multiplexed nanophotonic biosensor has been successfully implemented for simultaneous real-time monitoring of up to seven individual BiMW sensing waveguides. The photonic chip design, based on straight BiMW interferometers, incorporates on-chip Y-branches for light splitting, enabling parallel readout of multiple sensors. To advance towards an integrated prototype, a custom photodetector array was developed to enable continuous simultaneous acquisition of eight BiMW interferometers (seven sensors plus one reference), providing stable and reliable modal interferometric signals without optical crosstalk. To facilitate routine operation and robust measurements, a compatible microfluidic system was designed and fabricated, supporting high device operability. The fully integrated prototype exhibits low noise levels ($\sigma = 0.003 \pm 0.003$ rad) and a bulk LOD of $(7 \pm 5) \times 10^{-7}$ RIU, comparable to single-sensor performance and demonstrating that multiplexing does not compromise sensitivity. A detailed biosensing demonstration employing a simplified configuration in which all sensors were identically functionalized with the same antibody showed very low variability and good reproducibility between waveguides, both in the receptor immobilization and for target detection. The biosensor achieved rapid (<9 min) detection of RSV B nucleoprotein with an average LOD of 1.2 ± 0.4 ng·mL $^{-1}$ across the seven sensors. Blind sample testing further confirmed excellent accuracy and reproducibility. Further steps will focus on selective, controlled biofunctionalization of individual waveguides, enabling true multiplexed detection of different target analytes on a single multiplexed photonic chip. This work demonstrates the sensor platform potential for high-performance, parallel biosensing in real-time applications, highlighting its robustness, scalability, and readiness for complex bioanalytical tasks.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acssensors.6c01059>.

Reagents, microfluidic fabrication, biofunctionalization details, data analysis, and figures and tables supporting the reported work; Figure S1: Photograph of the multiplexed BiMW biosensor device, highlighting its main components; Figure S2: Propagation field simulations of the S-shaped Y-branch splitters; and Table S1: Overview of recent multiplexed silicon photonic biosensors, comparing their photonic configurations, multiplexed capabilities, resolution, and limits of detection for each target (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): A.A.F., P.R.P, M.C.E. and L.M.L. have filed a PCT patent related to the multiplexed BiMW sensor, PD array, and cartridge integration. P.R.P, M.C.E. and L.M.L. declare that they are co-Founders and hold interest in EROICA Dx S.L. that have licensed the patent application. Other authors declare no conflicts of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge EU financial support (Horizon Europe project NIAGARA No. 101082015), the Ministry of Science, Innovation, and Universities (MICIU), AEI, and the European Union Next Generation (EU/PRTR) (10.13039/501100011033) (Project PDC2023-133629-I00). The ICN2 is supported by the Severo Ochoa Centres of Excellence programme, Grant CEX2021-001214-S, funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039.501100011033.

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